

ASSESSMENT OF PERFORMANCE OF FERROCENE NANOPARTICLE -HIBISCUS CANNABINUS BIODIESEL ADMIXED FUEL BLENDED WITH HYDROGEN IN DIRECT INJECTION (DI) ENGINE

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Abstract

The excessive use of diesel fuel to generate significant amounts of energy results in increased gaseous emissions, which result in accelerated global warming, unfavorable climatic changes with attendant depletion in the global oil reserve. Owing to strict emission-policies, vehicle manufacturers are mandated to control emissions from diesel engines. To comply with such policies, one of the novel steps adopted in this study, is the use of hydrogen enriched biodiesel admixed with nanoparticles. Hydrogen is an excellent energy carrier for use in diesel engines operating in dual fuel mode. Previous works have also shown that the use of biodiesel-H₂ mix as fuel in diesel engines increases NO_x emissions. This research entails the use of ferrocene nanoparticle blended with hibiscus cannabinus as an alternative fuel while monitoring the resultant effects of varying hydrogen flow rates on the emission, combustion and performance of a direct injection (DI) engine. The nanoparticles were characterized, ultrasonicated and stabilized in the biodiesel. The blended nanofuel was admixed with a fixed volume of hydrogen at flowrates of 10 and 12 lpm in the intake air and further injected in the diesel engine. From the results, the biodiesel-snanoparticle biofuel (BN@50 ppm) blend gave low CO, NO_x, and HC emissions with an appreciable increase in the brake thermal efficiency (BTE). Furthermore, with hydrogen enrichment on BN@50 ppm at 10 LPM, (i.e., BNH@10 LPM), there was a marginal increase in the BTE (36 %) and a decrease in the CO (0.6 g/kWh), NO_x (163 g/kWh) and HC (18 g/kWh), emissions with improved combustion compared those of the diesel and biodiesel which confirm the suitability of BNH@10 LPM as alternative fuel for diesel. Thus, the use of BNH@10 LPM) fuel type can be used as the most efficient fuel in an unmodified diesel engine due to its high thermal efficiency and lowest emissions compared to other tested fuels.

Keywords: Diesel engine; Biodiesel; Ferrocene Nanoparticle; Emissions; Hydrogen.

1. INTRODUCTION

Energy production is crucial for the transportation sector with nearly 1.5 billion automobiles on the road amidst the current economic global expansion. Fossil fuel-powered engines and boilers emit a variety of toxic pollutants such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), hydrocarbons (HC), and particulate matter (PM), all of which are inimical to human health and the environment, thus resulting in cases such as lung cancer and destruction of the ecosystem [1,2]. The excessive use of diesel fuel to generate significant amounts of energy results in increased gaseous emissions, which result in accelerated global warming, unfavorable climatic changes with attendant depletion in the global oil reserve. The incessant increase in energy consumption has a consequential impact on the global economic security as well as the current fluctuation in oil prices [3]. Many countries have implemented stringent policies to meet the recent emission regulation standards due to other unforeseen expectations. Given the current difficulties and severe repercussions, a rapid shift from fossil fuels to innocuous alternative fuels is required [4 - 5]. Emission

reduction in diesel engines requires the following technologies/approaches; (i) To improve the quality of combustion through significant advances in the design of engine and fuel injector (ii) To use catalysts and filters on the exhaust gas line, however, these devices greatly affect engine performance negatively, (iii). The uses of additives such as hydrogen, and nanomaterials improve the performance of the engines as well as reducing engine emissions [2, 3, 5, 7]. Several studies on biofuel production and performance enhancement are in progress, however, the favorable nature of the environment and the availability of the biofuel source are quite essential. Biofuel, when used as fuel, does not release many hazardous gases into the atmosphere, which is why it is given utmost attention among several alternative fuels in modern-day research [6 -8]. The use of renewable fuels like biodiesel in diesel engines can significantly reduce toxic emissions. To lower engine emissions, it then becomes critical to consider replacing diesel with biodiesel in future engine-designs. Relative to diesel, biodiesel is non-toxic, sulfur-free, oxygenated and biodegradable [9]. However, the viscous nature of the latter, has an impact on its flow behavior, droplet properties, charge mixing quality and potential for disintegrating into droplets [10]. In the production of biodiesel, the type of raw material utilized, the method involved, and the formulation and process parameters all play a role in the yield and physicochemical qualities of the fuel. It is vital to recognize that, rather than growing a specific crop for the production of biodiesel, several crops, especially the locally accessible species, must be harnessed [3, 7, 11]. Hibiscus cannabinus is one of such crops that belongs to the cotton family, which flourishes best within 15 – 27 oC during its growth phase.

Jindal and Goyal [8] evaluated the emission and performance characteristics of hibiscus cannabinus/Ambadi seed oil biodiesel, in a Kirloskar TV1 diesel engine, their result showed lower performance and high emission characteristics for neat biodiesel fuel, with B20 having the highest performance and lower emission properties.

Investigation has shown that neat Ambadi biodiesel possesses low brake thermal efficiency (BTE) and relatively high NO_x emissions, high viscosity and density [8]. Therefore, there is need to combine the fuel with another fuel so as to overcome these limitations/shortcomings prior being used in a diesel engine, hence the reason for the introduction of ferrocene nanoparticle in the biofuel. The properties of ferrocene nanoparticle are presented in Table 1.

Nanotechnology has had a significant effect on the fields of industrial research. The emergence of novel nanotechnology products has been encouraged by the safe and cost-effective use of nanomaterials [2, 8]. Adding NPs to biodiesel has been shown in several experiments to improve the performance of an engine as well as emissions reduction [1, 3, 5, 7, 8]. These investigations also shown that adding this additive boosts the fuels heating value and cetane number, resulting in increased combustion efficiency. Some fuel qualities, such as viscosity, flash point, and density are improved by this addition [1,2, 9]. Due to a high cylinder pressure restriction, adding nanomaterials to the fuel reduces the ignition delay, enhances combustion speed, and increases heat release rate (HRR) [7]. Furthermore, biodiesel-added NPs can have high flash temperatures,

resulting in significant fuel storage and transportation improvements [4,10]. They also improve initial operation in cold weather settings by lowering the cloud point heat, increasing the surface area to size ratio, as well as improving the radiation/mass transfer properties, that will result in faster and better ignition [1, 11].

Elwardany et al. [12] investigated the influence of different ferrocene nanoparticle concentrations mixed with B30 and diesel fuels on their performance, emission and combustion characteristics when used as fuels in a 4-stroke engine. It was concluded that the BTE of the B30, increased by 2% owing to the addition of ferrocene nanoparticles whose optimum concentration was in the range of 250-300 mg/L. In terms of emission properties, ferrocene addition decreased the NO_x emissions while there was an increase in the carbon dioxide emissions for the diesel and B30 fuels at high and medium load conditions.

With the addition of 1% (weight basis) of ferrocene to diesel fuel, Furuhata et al. [13] found that the Sauter mean diameter (SMD) of soot particles decreased. This is line with the observations of Kasper et al. [14], who observed complete burning of carbonaceous materials in an acetylene flame seeded with ferrocene. Kim et al. [15] investigated the reactivity of carbon-based iron alongside soot particles. The activation energy of the oxidized soot was reduced significantly with 50 ppm of ferrocene. Hu et al. [16] studied the influence of ferrocene on the temperature of a rich mixture of propane/oxygen diffusion flames and soot formation. They observed that the flame temperature reduced, which prevented the smaller polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) from becoming larger. Morad and Sarhan [17] demonstrated that ferrocene derivatives had a corrosion-inhibiting action for steel. Their results also showed that there was a minimal improvement in the quality of the admixed ferrocene-biodiesel/diesel, in terms of the engine's combustion, emission and performance characteristics relative to the neat biodiesel/diesel fuel. Furthermore, the introduction of another fuel helps to reduce the kinematic viscosity of the blended fuels as well as their densities, with attendant increase in the fuel's cetane number and BTE, minimal engine-corrosion and other properties that will improve the fuel quality of ferrocene nanoparticle -hibiscus cannabinus (Ambadi) biodiesel in a DI engine, thus, hydrogen was introduced into the blended fuel. In air, H₂ has a flammability limit of 3.8 percent to 74.6 percent, whereas diesel fuel has a lower range of 0.8 to 4 percent by volume [7, 18]. Since H₂ has such a high burning velocity, it burns quickly. At room temperature, H₂ is a light gas with a lower density than natural gas and air. By cooling to a very low temperature at atmospheric pressure, the gas condenses to a liquid with a specific gravity of 0.07 [19, 20]. H₂ gas, thus, has a greater heating value of about 142 MJ/kg. The properties of H₂ are presented in Table 2.

Reports on the use of several biodiesel- nanoparticle blends have been carried out extensively for use in diesel engines to improve its combustion, emission and performance characteristic. However, considering the few existing literatures on the use of Ambadi biodiesel in neat or blended form (i.e., with diesel/biodiesel) that have been tested in diesel engines, there are no studies dedicated to the use of hibiscus cannabinus (Ambadi) – ferrocene nanoparticle blends in diesel engines. Also, till date, works have not

been reported on the use of Ambadi methyl esters - ferrocene nanoparticle blends agitated with hydrogen at different flowrates in a DI diesel engine in terms of its combustion, performance, and emission characteristics. The objective of this work is to sonicate Ambadi biodiesel blends with ferrocene nanoparticles that will augment the lapses of the biodiesel, thus improving the physicochemical properties of the nanofuel in terms of performance, combustion and emission characteristics when compared with those of diesel fuels. This aspect of research, has not been given full consideration and focus by other published literature. Furthermore, the nanofuel properties were optimized with hydrogen addition and varied at different flowrate, so as to improve the properties of the fuel in terms of combustion (shorter ignition delay, improved atomization), higher performance and minimal emission compared to the ferrocene nanoparticle- Ambadi fuel. Prior to blending, several preliminary assessments such as performance, combustion and emission characteristics were also conducted in order to establish the properties of the ferrocene nanoparticle- Ambadi biodiesel admixed hydrogen blend for optimum engine performance. Therefore, the aim of this research is to optimize the aforementioned fuel blend (Ambadi methyl esters- ferrocene nanoparticle mixed with hydrogen) for use in a Simpson S325 direct injection engine.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Transesterification of Hibiscus cannabinus (Ambadi) crude oil

Some harvested Hibiscus cannabinus (Ambadi) seeds were rinsed with water to remove particles, especially sand. The seeds were allowed to dry for three days to remove moisture and they were later dried at 110 °C in an oven for 2 h. Furthermore, the dried seeds were crushed and transferred to a mechanical press so as to extract the crude Hibiscus cannabinus (Ambadi) oil. After extraction, the oil was transesterified with 1 wt% KOCH₃ (catalyst) and 5:1 CH₃OH to oil molar ratio for one hour at 55 °C, to produce biodiesel. The produced biodiesel was then stored in a 2000 mL reagent bottle for further use.

2.2 Ferrocene-nanoparticles

Sigma Aldrich supplied the ferrocene nanoparticle with properties as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Characteristics of ferrocene nanoparticle

Parameter	Value
Density	1411 kg/m ³
Mol. Wt.	188 kg/kmol
Melting point	174 °C
Molecular formula	Fe(C ₅ H ₅) ₂
Boiling point	250 °C
Nano-size	12 nm

The ferrocene was characterize using the scanning electron microscope (SEM)- Thermo Fisher scientific, Viros 5 XHR SEM, USA, X-ray diffraction (XRD)- Siemens D-5000,

Malvern pan analytical, USA and Transmission electron microscope (TEM)- JEOL 2200FS Cryo-TEM JEOL Ltd, Tokyo, Japan respectively.

2.3 Preparation of the nanoparticle- biodiesel blends

Ferrocene nanoparticle was used in this study. Following the procedures described in the authors previous work [6], 200 mg of the nanoparticles were admixed with 1 L of biodiesel. The nanofluid preparation lasted for 32 h within which the fluids were treated with distilled water. A Sonics VCX 750 sonicator model was used in the homogenous mixing of the nanoparticles with the biodiesel for 30 minutes.

Hong et al. [21] reported that nanofluid stability can be enhanced at lengthier sonication times. Thus, prolonged sonication time prevents and reduces the agglomeration of particles. Ruan and Jacobi [22] reported that ultrasonication can prevent the agglomeration of particles, thus promoting stable nanoparticle distribution in the base fluids.

The addition of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) was necessary to instill stability and surface modification of the nanoparticles, so as to reduce possible coalescence and coagulation resulting from surface tension reduction.

Fig. 1 shows the schematic description for the preparation of the Ambadi biodiesel-ferrocene nanoparticle blends while fig. 2 depicts the ultrasound-assisted fuel-nanoparticle blend production unit.

Figure 1: Steps for the preparation of the Ambadi biodiesel-ferrocene nanoparticle blends.

Rotor 2: Transducer 3. Reactor 4. Inner protective sponge coating 5. Sonotrode 6. Biodiesel-NP blends in beaker 7. Thermocouple 8. Hot plate 9. Power source.

Figure 2: Schematic of ultrasound-assisted fuel-nanoparticles blend production unit.

2.4 Flowrate of hydrogen to sonicated biodiesel-ferrocene nanoparticle

2.4.1 Hydrogen characteristics

The hydrogen gas used for this research was purchased from BOC gas company with percentage purity of 99.98 %. Table 2 shows the characteristics of the H₂.

Table 2: Characteristics of H₂ gas obtained from BOC- gas company, Lagos, Nigeria

Parameter	Hydrogen fuel
Formula	H ₂
Mol. Wt. (g/mol)	2.012
Higher heating value (MJ/kg)	141.6
Kinematic viscosity at 25 °C (mm ² /s)	110
Boiling point (K)	20.27
Density(kg/m ³) at 1 atm and 25 °C	0.083
Stoichiometric air-fuel ratio	34.5
Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	181
Lower heating value (MJ/kg)	119.6

Note: All analyses to determine the properties of the hydrogen gas used were conducted at temperature room (28 °C) and at a pressure of 1 atm. Different mass flowrates (10, and 12) liters per minute (lpm) of hydrogen were employed in enriching the air inlet. The equal volume of hydrogen in the inducted air were kept constant at 10 vol/vol for all the hydrogen induced fuel mixtures. Due to the enrichment of H₂ of the intake air, the volume of consumed biodiesel was varied. The proportion of the volume of biodiesel-ferrocene nanoparticle added to H₂-air mix at the intake section are presented in a later section.

2.6 Experimental procedure

The experimental set-up of the flow-process is illustrated in fig. 3. The flowline of H₂ consists of a cylinder, flowmeter, pressure regulators, flame trapper and flame arrestor.

The supplied H₂ from BOC gas company limited, Lagos, Nigeria was pressurized in a high-pressure cylinder and released at an exit pressure of 2 bar with the aid of a pressure regulator. The specification of the engine is presented in Table 3, while the uncertainty measurements are tabulated in Table 4. The hydrogen flow rates of 10 and 12 lpm were delivered at high pressures to provide 10 % vol/vol each to 90 % biodiesel and biodiesel-nanoparticle mix. The produced nano fuels with the hydrogen were homogenized in a homogenizer which was agitated at 1500 rpm prior being introduced to the test engine. The produced fuels are presented in Table 3, while Table 4 shows the engine specifications.

Table 3: For emphasis; the blended ratio/proportion are as follows:

Parameter	Description	Acronym
D- 100	Diesel fuel	D- 100
B- 100	Ambadi (Neat biodiesel fuel)	B- 100
Biodiesel/nano-additive @ 50 ppm (A)	B-100 blended with 50 ppm ferrocene nanoparticle	BN@50 ppm
Biodiesel/H ₂ @ 10 lpm (B)	90 vol/vol bio-diesel blended with 10 vol/vol H ₂ at flow rate of 10 lpm	BH@10 lpm
Biodiesel/nano-additive @ 50 ppm/H ₂ @10 lpm (C)	90 vol/vol bio-diesel admixed with 50 ppm ferrocene nanoparticle and 10 vol/vol H ₂ at flow rate of 10 lpm	BNH@10 lpm
Biodiesel/nano-additive @ 50 ppm/H ₂ @12 lpm (D)	90 vol/vol bio-diesel admixed with 50 ppm ferrocene nanoparticle and 10 vol/vol H ₂ at flow rate of 12 lpm	BNH@12 lpm

Data acquisition systems (DAQ)

Figure 3: Schematic of the hydrogen flow line and Ambadi-nanoparticle fuel blends in diesel engine

Table 4: Engine specification

Engine make	Simpson S325
Stroke	4
Rated speed	1500 rpm
Injection nozzle diameter	0.3 mm
Displacement	0.638 L
Compression ratio	18:1
Nozzle operating pressure	200 – 225 bars
Bore diameter	87.5 mm
Injection pressure	205 bars
Cooling system	Water cooled
Cylinder	Single
Cylinder pressure transducer	0 – 360 bars
Rated power	5.5 Kw
Stroke length	110 mm
Injection timing	17 °bTDC

2.7: Uncertainty measurements

When obtaining readings or measurements from experiment, accidental/logical errors may ensue due to incorrect calibration of measurement devices. There are also variances in the design-precision and manufacture of equipment which makes them prone to errors while taking measurements, hence, experimental testing is important especially when evaluating uncertainties. When evaluating uncertainties, it is majorly determined by the measure of repeatability obtainable in three measurements with a low level of/insignificant magnitude of standard deviation. The method of Kline and McClintock (1) was adopted in calculating the percentage uncertainty of all measured parameters (Table 5).

$$\Delta T = \left[\left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} \Delta x_1 \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x_2} \Delta x_2 \right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x_n} \Delta x_n \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

Where ΔT represent the total uncertainty.

U – is dependent on the independent variables of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n

$\Delta x_1, \Delta x_2, \dots, \Delta x_n$ are the independent variable uncertainties.

Thus, the overall uncertainty is $\pm 0.71\%$

Table 5: The percentage uncertainty and accuracies of all measured parameters.

Properties	Accuracy (\pm)	Uncertainty (%)
Dynamometer (g)	$\pm 50g$	± 0.1
Measuring burette (cm ³)	± 0.25	± 0.2
Engine speed (rpm)	$\pm 10 rpm$	± 0.1
Pressure transducer (bar)	$\pm 0.1 bar$	± 0.1
Carbon monoxide emission (%)	$\pm 0.02\%$	± 0.3
Hydrocarbon emission (ppm)	$\pm 5 ppm$	± 0.2
NOx emission (ppm)	$\pm 5 ppm$	± 0.2
BTE (%)	–	± 0.2
BSEC (%)	–	± 0.3
Heat release rate (HRR)(J/°CA)	–	± 0.3
Crank angle encoder	$\pm 1^\circ$	± 0.02
Timer	$\pm 0.1s$	± 0.2

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Nanoparticle Characterization

The ferrocene nanoparticles were characterized using SEM, TEM and XRD in order to determine the structure and morphology of the nanoparticles (Fig. 4). The porous architectures of the nanoparticles were determined by looking at the surface morphology of the nanoparticle, which showed the textural and pore size arrangement of the nanoparticles [3]. The microstructure of the nanoparticle was determined using micrographs taken from scanning electron microscope (SEM) (fig. 4b). The TEM (fig. 4c) shows the nano-dispersed form of ferrocene. The XRD (fig. 3d) shows the inherent crystalline structure of ferrocene which showcases the crystalline phases present in the material.

Figure 4: Ferrocene (a) Structure (b) SEM (C) TEM (D) XRD patterns

3.2 Stability of the dispersed nanoparticle.

The stability of the dispersed NP in the biofuel was assessed using the UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Jenway 6850/230V) within a wavelength range of 200 to 1200 nm since the absorption band occurs within this limit. The surfactant tail group adsorbs onto the surface of the nanoparticle due to Van der Waals interactions [19 - 21]. The nano-fuel mixtures' stabilities were examined for 9 weeks and the absorbance-concentration profile is as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: The stability test of the tested blends (Ambadi blended with 50ppm ferrocene)

3.3 Fuel properties

The properties of the fuels that were measured include cetane number, density, kinematic viscosity, flash point, and calorific value for diesel, crude Ambadi, Ambadi methyl esters (Table 6). Those of the Biodiesel-nano-additive @ 50ppm, Biodiesel/H₂ @ 10 lpm, Biodiesel/nano-additive @ 50 ppm/H₂ @ 10 lpm and Biodiesel/nano-additive @ 50 ppm/H₂ @ 12 lpm are as presented in Table 7.

Table 6: Physicochemical properties of diesel crude Ambadi and Ambadi methyl esters

Parameter	Unit/ASTM	Conventional diesel	Crude Ambadi	Ambadi methyl esters
Calorific value	kJ/kg – D240	45000	39500	41600
Flash point	°C – D93	75	185	110
Density	kg/m ³ - D1298	824	941	893
Cetane number	D-976	49	33	44
Kinematic viscosity	(mm ² /s) – D445	3.4	16.3	7.1

Table 7: Properties of all blended fuels and their respective flowrates.

Parameter	Biodiesel-nano-additive @ 50ppm	Biodiesel/H ₂ @ 10 lpm	Biodiesel/nano-additive @ 50 ppm/H ₂ @ 10 lpm	Biodiesel/nano-additive @ 50 ppm/H ₂ @ 12 lpm
Calorific value (kJ/kg)	44300	44700	45100	44900
Density(kg/m ³)	846	834	821	826
Cetane number	51	52	53	52
Kinematic viscosity (mm ² /s)	3.2	3.0	2.31	2.8

3.4 Performance of the engine

3.4.1 Engine-BTE

BTE is a measure of how efficiently, a fuel burns inside the combustion chamber of an engine, and how the resulting heat is thus transformed into useful work. Some of the properties that influence engine-BTEs are calorific value, kinematic viscosity, oxygen content, cetane number (CN) and density of the fuel [4, 23]. The measured BTEs at several engine loads are as presented in Fig. 6. It was observed that the B100 fuel exhibited the worst performance characteristics amongst all the fuels. This can be as a result of the fuel having poor spray characteristics, thus resulting in lower energy content and higher viscosity of the neat biodiesel.

Also, generally, low CN is an indicator of poor ignition quality, thus affecting the delay period of fuel combustion which in turn translates to poor engine performance. Considering the recorded BTEs for other fuels, improved fuel-properties and quality were obtained compared to that of the neat biodiesel/diesel; the results are: biodiesel-nano-additive @ 50 ppm, Biodiesel/H₂ @ 10 lpm and Biodiesel/nano-additive @ 50 ppm/H₂ @12 lpm with corresponding BTEs of 32, 31 and 33% while that of the diesel fuel was 30 %. This is due to the presence of the nanoparticles and hydrogen in the biofuel [1, 6, 11, 16].

The biodiesel/nano-additive @ 50 ppm/H₂ @10 lpm gave the highest BTE of 36 %. The presence of H₂, ferrocene nanoparticle admixed in the biodiesel and the flowrate of hydrogen gave rise to high BTE in the fuel; this justifies the findings in ref. [8].

Figure 6: The variation of BTE with engine load.

3.2 Gaseous emissions

3.2.1 Carbon (II) oxide (CO) emission

Due to incomplete combustion of fuels, they produce carbon (II) oxide emissions. Diesel lacks oxygen molecule in its chain, thus producing high CO. The released carbon (II) oxide from DI engines is as a result of the limited O₂ that is needed to convert the released carbon (II) oxide during combustion [24]. Since Ambadi biodiesel has O₂ molecule in its structure, then there is the possibility of the fuel's ability to aid complete combustion, which in turn will give rise to low CO emissions compared to those of diesel fuel. Research has shown that oxygenated fuels can give up to 30 % reduced CO emissions depending on the engine-type, age and other conditions [3,11,13,16]. Fig. 7 is indicative of lower CO emissions for fuels associated with the Ambadi biodiesel. Higher emission of CO occurs in the diesel fuel due to lack of excess oxygen needed to convert the CO released from combustion. The presence of H₂ in the nanofuel drastically reduces the CO emission at a H₂ flowrate of 10 lpm compared to that of the diesel fuel. H₂ lacks carbon atoms, thus gives improved combustion rates. The decrease in CO emissions for the H₂-associated fuels, is due to the zero carbon atoms in H₂ as well as the high flame speed/wide flammability range of the H₂ gas. The CO emissions dropped by 2.4 %, 3.2 %, 10.6 % and 6.6% for the BN@50 ppm, BH@10 lpm, BNH@10 lpm and BNH@12 lpm fuels compared to that of the diesel fuel.

Figure 7: Variation of CO emissions with load.

3.2.2 Hydrocarbon emissions (HC emissions)

The unburnt HC emissions from the test engine fed with 6 different fuels are as shown in Fig. 8. UHC emissions are made up of incompletely combusted fuel, which is often generated at low power levels owing to the difficulties associated with mixing fuel and air [25]. Also, it is crucial to understand that (HC) emissions are influenced by the mixture's

air-fuel ratio. The amount of unburnt HC emitted by an engine is determined by the combustion characteristics of the fuel employed. Even though unburnt HCs react at above 65 °C in the presence of oxygen in the exhaust chamber, HC emissions from the tailpipe may be much lower than the HCs exiting the cylinder [13]. Based on the results, the hydrocarbon emissions decreased by increasing the hydrogen proportion in the biodiesel and biodiesel-nanoparticle blends due to their higher cetane rating, nanoparticle and hydrogen in the biodiesel, which then resulted in a decrease in the combustion delay [26 -27]. For the BN@50 ppm, BH@10 lpm, BNH@10 lpm and BNH@12 lpm fuels, the average reductions in hydrocarbon emissions are 27.1 %, 25.7%, 45.7% and 33. 51 % lower than that of pure diesel (B-100). These results corroborate the findings in refs. [17, 23]. This further shows that an increase in the hydrogen fraction, decreases the HC emissions in the fuel blends. Furthermore, hydrogen flowrate is another factor to be considered when dealing with HC emissions. Low carbon content of the fuels, increased fuel-air mixture uniformity, and high flame speed, significantly reduce combustion durations and the likelihood of incomplete combustion cycles, which may also contribute to the reduction in HC emissions caused by H₂ addition. Some other reasons behind this phenomenon include the fact that H₂ has a shorter quenching distance, which allows its flame to travel closer to the cylinder wall thus allowing for complete combustion.

Figure 8: Variation of HC emissions with load.

3.2.3 NO_x emissions

NO_x emissions are strongly influenced by combustion temperature, the fuel's physicochemical parameters and ignition delay. The biodiesel's higher kinematic viscosity and density, influenced its injection time, thus resulting in increased NO_x emissions [28]. Fig. 9 is an illustration of the NO_x emissions as a function of engine load for the DI engine.

The B100-fuel produced more NO_x than the diesel-fuel and this is due to its high oxygen concentration. It can be extrapolated from the results that NO_x emissions reduced as engine load increased for all the tested fuels.

This could be because, a higher load results in a higher combustion temperature inside the cylinder owing to the fact that a larger volume of fuel is burnt. Similarly, there is reduction in NO_x emissions for the biodiesel-nanoparticle fuels for the blend with 10 % vol/vol hydrogen fractions at different engine speeds (Fig. 9).

The average NO_x emissions for the BN@50 ppm, BH@10 lpm, BNH@10 lpm and BNH@12 lpm decreased by 2.2%, 3.6 %, 8.5 % and 5.1% respectively compared with that obtained for the diesel fuels. The addition of ferrocene nanoparticle, hydrogen and the influence of hydrogen flowrate are major determinants for improved fuel quality in terms of NO_x emission.

There was a marginal decrease in the emissions of the BNH@10 lpm compared to that of the BN@50 ppm due to the nanoparticle/hydrogen addition in the biodiesel. Most studies found that NO_x emissions varied depending on how much H₂ was blended in biofuels.

Some investigations however, reported an increase in NO_x emissions [1, 17, 22] as a result of increased combustion temperature, while others confirmed a reduction or no change when the H₂-flowrate was increased due to stable combustion at highly dilute conditions at low lean flammability of the hydrogen gas [3, 6,8, 13].

Figure 9: Variation of NO_x emissions with engine load.

Figure 10: Particulate emission

The variation of emission rate of smoke at various loads in the blended fuels are presented in figure 10. Increase in engine load, reduces the smoke formation. Additionally, the quantity of smoke opacity is inversely proportional to the percentage of added nanoparticle-biodiesel, thus leading to the reduction of smoke in the blended fuels. The lowest and highest smoke was achieved/emitted at BNH@10 LPM and D100. The product from incomplete combustion of unburned HC is emitted as smoke [12, 18]. At full load condition, the level of smoke was 1.9 %, 1.57 %, 1.42 % and 1.7 %, 1.02 % and 1.24 % for D 100, B100, BN@50 LPM, BH@10 LPM, BNH@10 LPM and BNH@12 LPM respectively. The nanoparticle enriched with hydrogen are responsible for low smoke emissions of the admixed fuels [4].

3.3 Combustion properties

3.3.2 Heat release rate (HRR)

At 100 percent load, Fig. 10 demonstrates the difference in rate of heat release in relation to the crank angle for the various fuel blends. The sooner the fuels diffuse rather than going through a lengthier pre-mix combustion phase, the greater the cetane number of the fuel blends [11, 29]. The HRR profiles of the blends show a similar trend to that of diesel, which is due to the shorter ignition delay of the fuel blends, which in turn influences the pre-mix burning peak phase pressure and HRR. Due to heat-absorption from the compressed hot air, negative HRRs were attained for all the test fuels throughout the delay period. Due to uncontrolled combustion, the HRR reached its peak after the delay period ended. After the TDC, the value of the HRR peaked at a few crank angle degrees. Due to the obvious premixed combustion, there was an additional release of heat at the second stage. The occurrence of H₂/nanoparticle in the biodiesel fuel made the fuels accumulate in the chamber at the time of premixed combustion phase, thus increasing

the HRR of the fuel blends [6,7,24]. At stage 2, a combined effect of diffused and premixed combustion of BNH@10 lpm, lead to a high heat release rate compared to diesel, BN@50 ppm, BH@10 lpm, and BNH@12 lpm. It can be observed that the maximum HRR was 74.1 J/deg. CA which was recorded for the BNH@10 lpm-fuel compared to that of the BN@50 ppm whose value is 66 J/deg. CA, BH@10 lpm with 64 J/deg. CA, BNH@12 lpm with 70 J/deg. CA while the diesel fuel had the lowest amongst them with a crank angle of 60 J/deg. CA.

Figure 10: Variation of HRR with the crank angle of the engine's shaft.

3.3.3 In-cylinder pressure variation

The in-cylinder pressure variation with crank angle at full engine-load is as illustrated in fig. 11. Factors such as delay period, fuel quality type, and operating conditions contribute to changes in in-cylinder gas pressure [30]. Considering the DI-engine, the amount of fuel burnt all through the premixed combustion phase, mainly impacts the peak pressure on the combustion rate at the beginning. As the engine load increases, the quantity of fuel that is burnt also increases, thus aggravating the pressure inside the cylinder in a gradual manner. According to some researchers, high peak cylinder pressures in the case of hydrogen-enriched biodiesel is vital in DI engine as a way of enhancing their ignition delays and exhaust gas temperatures [2, 7,11, 15]. When H₂ is used to enhance the performance of biodiesel fuels, it gives the possibility of a high peak pressure compared to other modes of fuel enhancement, owing to the reduction in delay period and enrichment in combustion by H₂. Ferrocene nanoparticle blended with Ambadi biodiesel was admixed with hydrogen at different flow rates, which thus improved the ignition delay period of the fuel-blends. Fuel-characteristics, such as higher volatility, low viscosity, quenching distance, higher flammability which are associated with hydrogen, makes it a

suitable blend for the nano fuels. These properties help to achieve complete combustion via rapid vaporization of the fuel mixtures [8,17,19, 22]. Therefore, higher cylinder pressures were noted for the BN@50 ppm, BH@10 lpm, BNH@10 lpm and BNH@12 lpm fuels, but more predominant for the BNH@10 lpm fuel, due to the nanoparticle-hydrogen mixture in the biodiesel as well as the variation in H₂-flowrate. 75.2 bar was the maximum in-cylinder pressure that was obtained for the BNH@10 lpm-fuel, while for the BNH@12 lpm-fuel, the measured pressure was 74.7 bar. Further increase in the flowrate and volume of hydrogen, reduced the calorific value of the fuel-blends, which resulted in the reduction of the in-cylinder pressure of the engine.

Figure 11: Variation of combustion pressure with crank angle of the engine's shaft.

3.4 Effects of exhaust emissions and engine modification to the environment

Vehicle exhaust emissions occurs as a result of incomplete combustion which affects living organisms, they include; particulate matter, CO, NO_x, SO_x, and various HCs, including volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) [4, 17]. Environmental factors such as temperature and weather conditions, as well as engine condition at the time of combustion, affect the levels of particulate matter found in motor vehicle emissions. Furthermore, depending on the volume and kind of traffic in a given region, the population's susceptibility to these emissions will vary significantly [25]. As the ability to detect and monitor personal exposures within communities has grown, the health effects of exhaust emissions have recently become apparent. As a result, more stricter rules have been enacted to decrease the risk of motor vehicle pollution to public health [27]. The fuel composition has been modified to limit the quantity these emissions. Improvements in engine design, have resulted in significant reductions in the amount of HC, NO_x, and CO produced [33]. Governments throughout the world continue to place a high importance on continuous monitoring and analysis of these pollutants produced by motor vehicles, as well as the adoption of effective remedies such as improved vehicle design and fuel modification.

Table 8: Documentation of some relative findings from other works on hydrogen fuel addition in biofuels

Type of fuel	Engine type/specification	Tested variables	Key findings	Refs.
Biodiesel + hydrogen	DI, 4- stroke, cylinder inline	The impact of different H ₂ volume fractions on engine performance and emissions.	Increasing the fraction of H ₂ also increases the peak cylinder pressure. BTE [↓], CO [↓] soot levels [↓] NO _x [↑],HRR[↑]	[31]
Water biodiesel emulsion + biogas	DI, water cooled variable compression ratio (VCR) diesel engine	The effect of pilot fuel replacement, peak cylinder Pressure, performance, ignition delay, emissions, the biogas flow rate,	Using emulsified biodiesel as a pilot fuel presented as follows: BTE [↑], BSFC [↓], CO [↓] soot levels [↓] NO _x [↓] and increases the peak cylinder pressure.	[32]
Di Ethyl Ether (DEE) + hydrogen	4-strokes, naturally aspirated constant speed D.I. water cooled Kirloskar, AV1, single cylinder diesel engine.	To optimized injection quantity, injection duration and injection timing of the fuel in port injected operated engine using diethyl ether as fuel source for H ₂ .	Engine was operated with DEE and H ₂ in dual fuel mode. BTE [↑],NO _x [↓], soot levels [↓], HC [↓] CO ₂ [↓] and CO [↓]	[33]
Diesel/Biodiesel fuel (BD-40) + H ₂ (2 LPM)	4-strokes, naturally aspirated constant speed D.I. water cooled Kirloskar, AV1, single cylinder diesel engine.	Variable engine loads were assessed based on engine emissions and performance	H ₂ + BD40 gives BTE [↑], BSEC [↓], soot levels [↓], HC [↓] and CO [↓]	[34]
Diesohol (E15D85) + H ₂	The use of AVL BOOST simulator was used to model the engine.	Effects of H ₂ enriched diesohol fuel on engine emissions	The use of (E15D85) enriched H ₂ gives; NO _x [↓], soot levels [↓], HC [↓] CO ₂ [↓] and CO [↓] and BTE [↓].	[35]
H ₂ +B100 (Mahua biodiesel) and H ₂ -B80E20)	A 4-stroke DI diesel type Kirloskar TAF 1, single cylinder.	The effect H ₂ enriched ethanol and Mahua biodiesel on engine emission and performance.	H ₂ addition to B100 resulted to BTE [↑] and NO _x [↑]. Ethanol addition to biodiesel blend gives NO _x [↓].	[36]
Microalgae Chlorella vulgaris (B100) + hydrogen	3 LD 510 Lombardini 4-Stroke, DI engine	H ₂ enriched biodiesel emission and performance on CI engine	H ₂ enriched biodiesel causes NO _x [↑], soot levels [↓], HC [↓] CO ₂ [↓] and CO [↓].	[37]
Ferrocene-nanoparticle + hydrogen.	A 4-stroke DI diesel type Simpson S325, single cylinder.	The impact of different H ₂ volume fractions on engine performance and emissions	Using emulsified biodiesel as a pilot fuel presented as follows: BTE [↑], HC [↓] CO [↓], NO _x [↓] and increases the peak cylinder pressure.	This study

4. CONCLUSION

This work investigates the impact of H₂ addition in ferrocene-biodiesel blends in a direct injection engine with the aim of achieving high performance, improved combustion and low emission characteristics. The study reveals that enhanced performance of the biofuel was seen for the ferrocene-biodiesel blends at the different flowrates of H₂ 10 and 12 lpm which gave high BTEs and low CO, HC, and NO_x emissions. The volume of hydrogen was maintained at 10 vol/vol before admixing it with the nano-fuels.

Other conclusions can be summarized as follows:

- The BTE of all the blended fuels increased and there was a marginal increase in the BTE of the hydrogen admixed ferrocene-biodiesel compared with that of the conventional diesel. Thus, the BTE of the BNH@10 lpm was 20.3% higher than that of the diesel fuel which is consistent with higher O₂ content and lower calorific value of the fuel.
- The ferrocene-biodiesel blends mixed with H₂ gave the lowest HC, NO_x and CO emissions. However, for the neat biodiesel, the NO_x emission increased significantly compared to those of the diesel fuel. All the tested fuel-blends gave low HC, NO_x and CO emissions as against the high emissions which were recorded for the diesel fuel.
- Due to improved fuel properties, there was an appreciable level of improvement in the combustion of the fuel blends thus leading to a shorter ignition delay for all the blends.

Finally, results show that the addition of hydrogen to the ferrocene-biodiesel mix is vital and crucial in obtaining a fuel-blend that can boost engine performance in a DI engine and hence, comes off as an alternative fuel in such systems.

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